

RURAL LIBRARIES IN CHIKKABALLAPUR DISTRICT: BROADCASTING ECONOMIC INFORMATION TO RUSTICAL COMMUNITIES – A LITERATURE SURVEY

Dr. Ravikumar N.S.,

Librarian at the Government First Grade College in Yelahanka, Bengaluru- 560064,
Karnataka, India.

Dr. Ningayya,

Librarian at the Government First Grade College in Yelahanka, Bengaluru- 560064,
Karnataka, India.

ABSTRACT

The study aims to inform the rural population in Chickaballapur District about the rural economy through rural libraries. Research objectives include understanding the socio-economic and cultural background of rural residents, identifying library users in gram panchayats, assessing their education levels, determining their preferred information sources, evaluating the impact of media on respondents, identifying other sources of information used, assessing the influence of news channels, evaluating the usefulness of gram panchayat libraries, identifying users, obstacles in accessing information, time spent in libraries, and ideal ways of providing information. The study utilized resources such as Library and Information Abstracts (LISA), books, and journals from 1936 to 2012 to inform the research design and gather 58 diverse reviews based on various criteria. Primary data will be collected through surveys in Chikkaballapur district, Karnataka. The study will review existing literature on gram panchayat libraries, use open-ended questionnaires for data collection, and is structured into five chapters covering the study area, literature review, area profiling, data analysis, and conclusions.

Keywords: Rural libraries, Chikkaballapur, rural economy, gram panchayats, information access, media impact, library users.

Cite this Article: Ravikumar, N.S., & Ningayya. (2024). Rural libraries in Chikkaballapur district: Broadcasting economic information to rustical communities – A literature survey. *Journal of Library and Information Science Technology*, 6(2), 14–27.

https://iaeme.com/MasterAdmin/Journal_uploads/JLIST/VOLUME_6_ISSUE_2/JLIST_06_02_002.pdf

1. INTRODUCTION

This review evaluates the role of rural libraries in providing economic information to rural communities. Conducting a literature review is essential for understanding previous research in the field, offering insights and recommendations. We utilized resources such as Library and Information Abstracts (LISA) and Library and Information Science Technology Abstracts (LISTA) from 1936 to 2012. Studies on Grampanchayat libraries' awareness and utilization were summarized, along with research on open-source software for libraries. The review focuses on these key areas:

- ✓ Rural Library Services
- ✓ Public Library
- ✓ Rural Economics or Libraries
- ✓ Information Needs
- ✓ User Studies
- ✓ Dissemination of Information
- ✓ Information Technology
- ✓ Information Resources
- ✓ Information Literacy
- ✓ Mobile Library Services
- ✓ Gram Panchayat Libraries

Through these studies, we seek to understand how rural libraries can better provide economic information and serve their communities. Public libraries offer a range of services, including books, digital resources, educational programs, and community events, promoting literacy, lifelong learning, and community engagement. They bridge the digital divide by providing technology and internet access, promoting digital literacy, and ensuring equal opportunities for all community members. Public libraries contribute to education, cultural enrichment, and social inclusion by offering free access to information for the well-being and development of individuals and communities.

2. RURAL LIBRARY SERVICES

Robert Maynard Hutchins (1936) highlights the dynamic nature of libraries and their role in promoting reading for various purposes such as education, information, status, emotional release, self-realization, and spiritual growth. The library is essential for the development of intellectual, moral, aesthetic, social, and political values. The relationship between writer and reader is significant, and the library plays a crucial role in fostering this relationship as a social agency. Public libraries stimulate reading habits among the public through their network of branches, distribution points, book-mobiles, and outreach programs. In a rapidly changing society, the library serves as a key institution in meeting the increased demand for knowledge and information, adapting to societal changes, and initiating ideas rather than just providing books.

Leon Carnovskr (1963) in his work, "The Medium-Sized Public Library - Its Status and Future" emphasized the rising demand for library services for children and young people. The projected 92% increase in the population of children aged five to seventeen by 1980, compared to 1950, will lead to a 105% rise in school enrollment. Post-World War II advancements in

science and technology have sparked a greater interest in learning, driving up the demand for reading materials. This trend will impact library usage and the types of collections available for young readers. Children's book selections prioritize quality over quantity, making it challenging to balance variety and quality. To meet the growing needs of the youth population, libraries must significantly expand their collections and offer a wider range of books. Adapting to the continuous growth in population and school enrollment is essential for libraries to provide adequate resources for children and young people.

Mukherjee (1966) emphasizes the symbiotic relationship between libraries and education, considering them as interconnected services. He underscores the role of both formal and informal education in building self-confidence in individuals. Mukherjee highlights how informal education fosters qualities like self-help, self-confidence, self-reliance, and initiative. He argues that public libraries play a vital role in lifelong learning for people of all ages, serving as a center for intellectual growth and curiosity. Mukherjee suggests that just as society provides basic necessities, it also has a moral duty to educate its citizens and offer mental nourishment through educational institutions and libraries. According to Mukherjee, a modern society flourishes when it prioritizes the physical, mental, and intellectual well-being of its populace.

Steels Pinches (1966) examined the growth of children's libraries in the UK, USA, and other countries in his book "Library Work with Young People." He discussed key events that influenced the development of children's libraries. In the 19th century, children's library provision in Britain was sporadic, with Mechanics institutes and the Sunday school movement playing important roles. Industrialization, new railways, and immigration from 1870-1910 impacted the evolution of children's libraries. Challenges included immigrant communities, minority groups, and urban-rural disparities. The IFLA publication "Library Service to Children" is a valuable resource on children's library services. In France, children's libraries were limited before 1919, as book provision was part of the educational curriculum. After World War I, public library services emerged through donations, as discussed in G. Rees and Marcel Bouyssi's 1964 article. L'Heure Joyeuse, a 1924 American gift to French children, established a collection of children's books and activities to promote literacy and engagement with libraries.

Shera (1972) discusses in "Foundations of Education for Librarianship" how libraries can meet the expectations of modern society, which include promoting self-governance, truth-seeking, unity of means and ends, non-violence, knowledge, generosity, tolerance, reverence, and freedom of thought and expression. Libraries serve as a vital resource in achieving these values by providing access to various forms of communication and knowledge transmission. Shera outlines the key roles of libraries as: assembling, organizing, preserving, and providing access to information; transmitting knowledge across generations; accumulating and building upon knowledge; supporting contemporary knowledge development; and conserving research time by facilitating literature searches.

Spatz (2000) it was noted that the delivery of consumer health information in rural areas is influenced by both lifestyle and geography. The Planetree Health Resource Center, a community-based consumer health library affiliated with a small rural hospital, has been serving the public in a rural setting for eight years. One key aspect of providing consumer health information in rural areas is building relationships with community members to establish credibility and ensure sustainability. The resource center takes a proactive approach by engaging in various outreach efforts to strengthen its ties with the community and collaborates with other organizations, such as schools, to enhance health information delivery. This article provides an overview of the Planetree Health Resource Center's strategies for rural outreach.

Uhegbu (2001) examines the obstacles to rural information services for community development in Nigeria. He identifies key components of community information and highlights challenges such as negative perceptions towards information, poor infrastructure, government indifference, and internal rivalries. Uhegbu recommends utilizing traditional institutions and town development associations to improve information dissemination in rural areas.

Mokgaboki (2002) emphasizes the importance of community libraries and information services (CLIS) in rural and disadvantaged areas in South Africa. The study discusses the objectives of community libraries, challenges in securing government funding for CLIS, and the crucial role of the Directorate of Library and Heritage Services in supporting the success of CLIS.

Snyder (2004) examines rural library services for minority populations in the U.S. The case studies highlight the impact of immigration and changing demographics on library services. The census data provides insights into the needs of minority groups and the strategies for serving them.

Dent (2006) examines the Kitengesa Community Library in rural Uganda as a potential model for similar libraries in developing countries. The study uses the library as a case study to highlight characteristics of rural libraries identified by B.J. Mostert in a 1998 article. The research methodology includes focus groups, interviews, surveys, observation, and analysis of library data. The findings suggest that the Kitengesa Community Library is a successful model that could be replicated in other rural villages to benefit schools and communities. The paper also discusses implications for future research, such as the impact of the library on student achievement and teaching practices. The study underscores the importance of rural library services in promoting literacy and development in underdeveloped nations, particularly in Africa. The unique data from a two-year study of a small village library offers valuable insights for implementing rural library services.

Kumar (2006) offers a detailed analysis of the rural library movement in India, focusing on milestones, current status, legislative initiatives, and the role of library associations and professionals. The article emphasizes the importance of strategic planning and the establishment of Rural Library and Community Resource Centers (RLCRCs) in villages to promote reading and provide information. Kumar advocates for state governments to enact library legislation to ensure rural public library services are accessible and effective nationwide.

Kaula (2006) in his study explores the development of rural libraries in India. The study highlights the establishment of village libraries through the National Adult Education Program and various organizations in multiple states. It also discusses the implementation of library laws and the importance of rural libraries as community resource centers. The author suggests that the government conduct surveys to understand user needs and establish information centers to educate rural populations, including women, children, skilled workers, farmers, and individuals with disabilities.

Standerfer (2006) in her article explores how the information age has transformed rural libraries into fully equipped information centers. The shift has impacted the nature of these libraries and their services, particularly in reference services. The article questions whether rural libraries can meet the increasing demand for information consumption in the digital age, despite having internet access. Using examples from libraries in central and northern Illinois, it compares the evolution of reference services in rural public libraries to those in small urban libraries.

Maria and Ramhab (2007) implemented the Library Service System for Rural Areas in Bacs-Kiskun County, Hungary. The model introduced a new library and information service center

in a small village, supported by the county library. The article emphasizes the benefits of professional assistance, quality services, and state funding for the village library.

Ebiwolate (2010) discusses the significance of public library services in rural areas, particularly in the Niger River Delta region of Nigeria. The article emphasizes the importance of library infrastructure, information and communication technologies (ICT), and literacy programs in rural areas to improve quality of life and contribute to socioeconomic development. It mentions various library services such as bookmobiles, information and referral services, outreach programs, children's library services, and selective dissemination of information (SDI). The challenges of inadequate funding and a lack of trained personnel in Nigeria are also addressed, along with recommendations for improving library services.

Zabed Ahmed (2010) in a study the performance and impact of three community-led library initiatives in Central Thailand were assessed using a mix of quantitative and qualitative methods. Exit interviews with library users and community leaders were conducted to gather feedback on library collections, performance, and challenges faced in accessing the libraries. The findings suggested that small-scale community-run libraries can positively impact community development. The study proposed a model for community libraries to enhance services and support rural development in Thailand and beyond.

Clarke (2011) examines the challenges of achieving equality of access in libraries amidst regional and urban-rural disparities in China. The study analyzes economic gaps and their impact on library resources and services, comparing funding, collections, and space data. It also evaluates government policies and the library profession's responses to address these inequalities. The article concludes that true equality of access requires proactive efforts beyond mere commitment to inclusivity in the face of significant social disparities.

Islam (2012) examines library services in rural Bangladesh. The paper discusses rural library services and presents findings from focus group discussions in ten northern communities. The study reveals the information needs, reading habits, and awareness of rural library activities among participants. Results show that rural libraries are vital for meeting community information needs and promoting educational development. This study is the first to use focus group discussions to evaluate the impact of rural library activities in Bangladesh, highlighting the effectiveness of this method.

Kunhambu (2012) highlights the vital role of education in holistic individual development. Public libraries should act as a catalyst for this growth, catering to diverse segments of society, including the illiterate, newly literate, semi-skilled, children, youth, and housewives. Libraries can promote reading habits in rural areas through book distribution and engaging displays. In India, rural communities rely on small enterprises and agriculture for economic sustenance. Therefore, library materials should focus on topics like improved farming techniques, new seed technology, health, family planning, cultural values, small savings, and social issues. Addressing the education gap is crucial for the progress of developing countries, emphasizing the importance of literacy and information literacy. Developing nations should prioritize support for rural and school libraries to empower these communities towards self-sufficiency.

Mehra & Nolt (2011) discuss a grant from the Institute of Museum and Library Services Laura Bush 21st Century Librarian Program awarded to the University of Tennessee's School of Information Sciences. The \$567,660 grant, titled "Rural Library Professionals as Change Agents in the 21st Century," aims to train 16 paraprofessionals from rural libraries in the Southern and Central Appalachian region. The program runs from June 2010 to August 2012 and involves a part-time master's degree program through UT's SIS synchronous distance education program. The grant focuses on integrating information technology competencies in

rural librarianship and includes five phases: recruitment needs assessment, educational activities, mentoring, evaluation, and dissemination of results.

Shaifuddin (2011) examines the perspectives of rural youth in Malaysia on information sources and library services. The study emphasizes the significance of library resources in enhancing knowledge. It identifies shortcomings in rural libraries, including limited computer access, library materials, and facilities. The research underscores the importance of continuous educational support for rural youth and their reliance on the Internet for information access.

Unagha & Ibenne (2011) examine the information-seeking behaviors of rural communities in Nigeria and the barriers to delivering development information to these populations. The study highlights the potential of providing information to rural communities for economic reconstruction in developing countries, the challenges of low literacy rates in accessing information channels, and the struggle for rural individuals to appreciate the value of information and technology over tangible agricultural products.

3. PUBLIC LIBRARY

George Jefferson (1969) discusses the evolving role of libraries as organizations rather than just physical institutions. He emphasizes the importance of libraries adapting to new forms of media to remain relevant, suggesting they redefine themselves as multi-media centers. Jefferson references an issue of *Library Trends* from October 1967, where the editor, C. Walter Stone, explores the redefinition of the library function in the context of new communication media. Stone concludes that the library's function, focusing on knowledge assessment, storage, retrieval, and rapid transmission, will be more critical than the physical library itself. This shift highlights the changing role of public libraries as social institutions concerned with cultural standards. Jefferson's insights underscore the importance of adapting to new media and redefining the library function to meet the evolving needs of society.

Campbell (1973) highlighted the importance of public library systems in urban metropolitan areas for providing access to information. Metropolitan areas have historically been at the forefront of library service development due to their larger market and diverse population. Public library systems in metropolitan centers have evolved into large-scale institutions, with over 150 such services worldwide. The concept of a system of free libraries has been widely adopted in metropolitan cities to serve large populations effectively. To bridge the urban-rural resource gap and improve quality of life, establishing free public library systems in rural areas is crucial.

Pandey (1985) explores the historical lack of library services for the poor and common people in ancient times. He highlights the British efforts to establish public libraries to improve accessibility. Libraries in ancient and medieval times were typically private collections managed by royalty, wealthy individuals, and scholars, limiting access. The British introduced public library institutions in India, initially serving the upper class and elites. These initiatives laid the foundation for the development of libraries accessible to the general population.

Khanna (1987) explores the historical role of libraries in providing religious and moral education in various civilizations. Monastery and church libraries have traditionally supported this purpose, as have libraries associated with ashrams and religious institutions in India. In democratic societies, public libraries play a vital role in informing citizens and enabling them to exercise their rights effectively. Western public libraries excel in providing free access to information for all community members, influencing attitudes, promoting equality, social awareness, and education. They serve as agents of social change by bridging gaps between different groups and promoting inclusivity through access to relevant resources.

Vavrek (1995) highlights the challenges rural and small libraries in the United States face. The study emphasizes their vital role in providing information services and reviews reports on the information needs and role of rural public libraries.

Jatana & Khosla (2003) highlight the vital role of public libraries in uplifting rural India. These libraries serve as intermediaries connecting various agencies in villages and play a crucial role in disseminating information, preserving cultural heritage, enhancing vocational skills, and promoting learning and literacy. They are essential for providing informal education to illiterate adults, bridging the education gap, and promoting individual development. Mobile library units can further enhance the impact of public libraries in rural areas by providing educational and entertaining reading material.

4. RURAL ECONOMICS OR LIBRARIES

Mazie & Ghelfi (1995) emphasize the importance of rural libraries in providing information access to rural communities. They discuss the economic and social challenges in rural America and the role of information access in improving global competitiveness.

Takalkar & Devi (2001) studied rural libraries in four Indian states, emphasizing the importance of information for socio-economic development in areas where 70% of the population resides. Traditional rural libraries are inadequate to meet diverse information needs due to limited resources and lack of library legislation. The study examines the current state of rural libraries, information needs, and information-seeking behavior, suggesting the use of IT techniques to enhance services. Findings show rural libraries face resource and staffing challenges, with information on development schemes, employment, education, and health being top priorities. Mass media and personal networks are key information sources. The study recommends transforming existing libraries or establishing modern information centers with IT tools to better serve rural communities.

Islam & Uddin (2005) analyzed information support services in rural development libraries in Bangladesh, specifically in Dhaka, Comilla, and Bogra districts. They assessed the impact of technology on these libraries, identified tools and techniques used to meet information needs, and outlined challenges and recommendations for improvement.

Kumar (2005) conducted a study on Rural Library and Community Resource Centers (RLCRCS) in India, focusing on states with library legislation. The research aimed to understand the information needs and challenges faced by rural communities, evaluate the impact of Government programs, and assess the role of NGOs in providing information services. The study sought to develop a model for a Rural Library and Community Resource Centre.

5. INFORMATION NEEDS

Durrani (1985) examines the information needs of rural populations in both developed and developing countries. The articles focus on information systems in Kenya, rural information services in Great Britain, and the operations of public libraries, a community college library, and a mining company information service in Australia.

Alemna (1991) in his study investigates information provision in rural Ghana by governmental and non-governmental organizations. The study focuses on agricultural, veterinary, health, and education officers delivering information to rural communities. Alemna notes that information reaches rural areas but questions its reliability and effectiveness in meeting objectives.

Sturges (1996) conducted a study in Malawi to help the National Library Service provide information to rural communities more effectively. The research aimed to understand the communication process between government information providers, intermediaries, and

villagers. By analyzing feedback and experiences, the study identified areas for improvement in information dissemination.

Asamoah-Hassan (1997) explores the role of libraries in educating rural individuals in Ghana, focusing on the Ghana Library Board's efforts and limitations. Traditional library services are seen as inadequate for modern information dissemination, prompting the need for new approaches like extension activities. The involvement of rural residents in planning and implementing information delivery strategies is crucial. Challenges to effective information access for rural populations are identified, with recommendations for solutions.

Anwar (1998) investigated the information needs of rural Malaysians in three villages lacking library services. Despite existing literature on rural libraries, research on rural information needs is limited. The study reviewed 33 relevant studies and shared findings from a 1996 survey in Malaysia. Data from 108 individuals in 300 households revealed their top information needs, reasons for seeking information, and preferred sources. The study highlighted that 93.4% of participants expressed interest in using a library if accessible. Understanding rural populations' information needs is crucial for designing effective library services in rural areas.

6. USER STUDIES

Kawatra (1992) emphasizes the challenges of meeting users' information needs and the importance of conducting user studies in his book 'Library User Studies: A Manual for Librarians and Information Scientists.' The increasing complexity of information needs is influenced by factors such as the growing volume and complexity of literature, scattered information sources, language barriers, and access issues. To effectively cater to user needs, a strong connection between information resources and users is essential, focusing on accuracy, relevance, and availability. User studies help identify strengths and weaknesses of library resources and services, user needs, faculty and student priorities, barriers to library use, and levels of engagement in library programs. These studies aid in improving organization and planning for library services at local and national levels, emphasizing the importance of proactively addressing future information demands.

7. DISSEMINATION OF INFORMATION

Wilson and Stephenson (1965) in "Dissemination of Information" explore various methods of sharing information within organizations, emphasizing the importance of sources such as books, periodicals, reports, conference papers, and professional meetings. These sources provide valuable information through papers and discussions at events like conferences, symposia, and congresses.

Anwar (1976) suggested using local libraries as information centers for rural development in Pakistan. These libraries would offer literacy programs, adult education, Open University courses, agricultural training, and general information services. Each center would have a television for educational content and be managed by a tutor-librarian. The libraries would be part of a national information system hierarchy, including tehsil, district, provincial, and national libraries. The proposal includes a budget, excerpts from national education policies, and details on a library-based independent study program in Chicago.

Diakite (1995) studied the dissemination of information in rural Mali through public libraries and rural audio libraries. Mali has been establishing public libraries since 1977, including a mobile rail library, to promote reading nationwide. The rural audio libraries project, initiated in 1982 by Mali and UNDP, provides information to rural communities through radio-cassettes. The study explores how public libraries and audio libraries meet the information needs of both literate and non-literate populations, and strategies for training and educating different segments. It discusses the history of Operation Lecture Publique, the three levels of the Malian

public library network, librarian training, library contents, costs, and reading promotion initiatives. The study also covers the rural audio libraries project, which aims to empower rural communities with modern and traditional knowledge in their languages to promote rural development.

Balakrishnan (2001) emphasized the importance of data collection, government involvement in disseminating scientific information, and the role of technology in benefiting communities. He highlighted the unequal global distribution of information resources and the potential of information technology to improve societal infrastructure, industries, knowledge, and culture. Governments should engage local communities and professionals in implementing and operating these technologies to maximize their impact on society. Ultimately, the impact of information technology on humanity depends on individual utilization.

Ray (2005) examines Rabindranath Tagore's rural development program in India, initiated in 1921 at Sriniketan. Tagore aimed to empower villagers for self-reliance and development in various aspects. The paper delves into the collection, sharing, and utilization of information in rural Bengal to create and implement development plans. It also highlights the Rural Reconstruction Centre's role in disseminating information to rural communities.

Ajuwon (2006) addresses the difficulties of spreading HIV/AIDS information in rural Nigerian communities. Education is vital for prevention due to the lack of a cure or vaccine. Current media campaigns focus on urban areas, neglecting rural populations. The paper proposes alternative approaches, including leveraging traditional communication channels like family leaders, youth groups, faith-based organizations, market women associations, and farmers clubs. It also emphasizes the potential of librarians and Information and Communications Technology in effectively disseminating HIV/AIDS information.

Tella (2007) discusses the importance of indigenous knowledge (IK) in rural development and highlights the efforts of the National Institute of Rural Development (NIRD) in promoting and sharing IK with rural communities. The paper explores NIRD's initiatives in developing traditional practices such as mud houses, handmade paper, vermicompost, and medicinal plants nursery. It also addresses key issues related to the collection, recording, storage, and documentation of IK, as well as challenges related to intellectual property rights and dissemination. The role of Information and Communication Technologies (ICTs) in preserving and sharing IK is also discussed, with a proposal for establishing a digital information resources base on IK.

Etebu (2009) examines how traditional African communication methods contribute to sustainable development in rural communities in Bayelsa State, Nigeria. The article discusses the use of town criers, gongs, drums, and community meetings as traditional indicators for information dissemination. It also explores the changes in communication practices during colonial times.

8. INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY

Kiplangat (1999) studied the use of information technology (IT) to improve access to agricultural information in rural Kenya. The research explored various IT tools like CD-ROMs, computer networks, and expert systems. Case studies of organizations using IT for agricultural information dissemination were conducted. The study highlighted benefits and challenges of IT adoption in rural areas, emphasizing the importance of aligning technology with community needs. Key advantages of IT included data storage, communication, and user-friendly interfaces. The study emphasized user-centric IT solutions for rural development.

Snyman (2003) emphasizes the significance of providing information to disadvantaged rural communities in South Africa. The Constitution guarantees the right to access information, and

information and communications technology (ICT) can enhance education, healthcare, and other services by improving the quality of information available. The article examines the government's efforts to enhance communication technology infrastructure for rural communities through a center-based approach, assessing both the successes and challenges of these initiatives.

Asaba & Others (2006) highlights the importance of agricultural production in East Africa for local consumption and export, impacting national economies. Agricultural information is crucial for improving small-scale production, connecting it to profitable markets, and enhancing rural livelihoods, food security, and national economies. The Comprehensive Africa Agricultural Development Programme (CAADP) emphasizes research, technology dissemination, and adoption to boost agricultural productivity and competitiveness. Rural knowledge centers play a key role in disseminating agricultural information to farming communities. This paper discusses strategies to promote access to agricultural information through these centers in Kenya and Uganda, offering print and electronic resources, including ICTs like computers, phones, and radios. Information is sourced from various channels, providing services such as technical assistance, market information, and Internet access. Sustainability depends on community engagement, capacity building, and user knowledge clubs to facilitate information access.

Juma & Kahinga (2006) discovered that information and communication technologies have transformed the way information is created, processed, and shared. These advancements have made information access and distribution faster and more accurate. Despite the benefits, Africa faces challenges in fully utilizing these technologies, particularly among rural farmers due to issues like poor telecommunication infrastructure and low literacy rates. This presentation focuses on the potential of using the Internet to establish online agricultural partnerships in developing countries. It highlights how the World Wide Web can facilitate networking among agricultural stakeholders and promote the adoption of modern agricultural practices. The presentation suggests creating an interactive website as a practical solution to enhance collaboration and knowledge sharing among agricultural stakeholders.

Akinbile & Otitolaye (2008) a study emphasized the importance of technology transfer in enhancing agricultural production. The research assessed the knowledge of extension agents in utilizing communication channels for sharing agricultural information. A structured questionnaire was administered to 80% of randomly selected extension agents from the Ogun State Agricultural Development Project. Data analysis involved descriptive and inferential statistics, including Chi-square and PPMC. The study revealed that farm visits and radio were the most commonly used communication channels by respondents. 78.8% of extension agents had moderate knowledge in using communication channels, with only 16.8% possessing a high level of knowledge. Agents demonstrated the highest proficiency in utilizing television (95.6%), interpersonal communication (85%), and radio (85%). The research also identified a significant correlation between the agents' knowledge level in communication channels and their educational background. To enhance the agents' proficiency in utilizing communication channels, it is recommended to promote further education and provide in-house training. This will enable them to effectively disseminate agricultural information and facilitate the diffusion of innovation.

Gadagin & Kamble (2008) in their study explore the impact of Community Information Centers on rural development in Karnataka State. They discuss the objectives and services of these centers, as well as the role of information and communication technology (ICT) in empowering rural communities. The study also examines government e-projects aimed at promoting electronic information resources and services in rural areas.

9. INFORMATION RESOURCES

Melanie Gardner (2000) in her article explores the Rural Information Center (RIC) at the National Agricultural Library, outlining its services, common requests, and the resources utilized to address them.

10. INFORMATION LITERACY

De Jager and Nasslmbenl (2001) conducted a study on Mpumalanga Provincial Library Services in South Africa, focusing on an information literacy intervention for library workers. The study aimed to enhance the skills of workers in rural areas to better serve diverse community needs. The paper discusses the identified information and training needs, campaign design, progress, outcomes, and evaluation. The study emphasizes the role of small public libraries and unqualified workers in addressing social exclusion in disadvantaged communities.

Dent (2007) explores the impact of rural libraries on economic development in Uganda, focusing on the Kitengesa Community Library. The study showcases how these libraries contribute to economic growth, education, and literacy in rural areas through small-scale projects at Kitengesa. The literature review discusses rural and economic development in Uganda, as well as the connection between literacy, libraries, and economic progress. Qualitative data from research at the Kitengesa Library in 2004 and 2005 are included, featuring insights from various stakeholders. The study suggests that rural community libraries can enhance local economic development, though long-term outcomes are uncertain. The projects at Kitengesa have inspired hope and potential among users, with implications for other rural libraries. Future research could involve a quantitative evaluation of the Kitengesa projects to further highlight the role of rural libraries in local economic development. This study underscores the importance of rural community libraries in providing information access and opportunities for economic advancement in underserved areas.

11. MOBILE LIBRARY SERVICES

Benstead (2004) studied alternative mobile library services for rural communities in England, focusing on best value, public library standards, and social inclusion policies. The research involved a questionnaire survey of librarians in rural public library authorities and case studies. Findings showed that social inclusion and best value reviews drove alternative service delivery in rural areas. Village halls were popular service locations, and ICT improved service delivery. However, some authorities did not consult rural users. The study highlights challenges and opportunities in providing library services to rural communities and the impact of government policies. Public library practitioners and researchers can gain valuable insights from this study.

12. GRAM PANCHAYAT LIBRARIES

Tadasad (2009) explores rural librarianship and its role in rural development. They stress the importance of establishing Gram Panchayat Libraries in rural areas to empower individuals and create an information-rich society. The study examines literature on rural libraries, with a focus on Karnataka, and highlights the impact of Gram Panchayat libraries in the Hyderabad Karnataka region. The authors commend the Department of Public Libraries for supporting active Gram Panchayat Libraries.

Shivalingappa Anupama (2009) in a study conducted an effort was made to assess the utilization of gram panchayat libraries in Gulbarga district by users based on their personal characteristics, frequency of library use, purpose of use, information services, and the effectiveness of the library system. The findings suggest the need for well-functioning gram

panchayat libraries and highlight the importance of user education programs to maximize the benefits of these libraries.

13. CONCLUSION

A literature review is a crucial component of research projects as it involves analyzing existing research and publications on the topic. This process helps researchers understand the current knowledge in the field, identify gaps, and build on previous work. It also allows researchers to identify key theories, concepts, and methodologies used in previous studies to inform their own research design and analysis. Additionally, a literature review helps researchers place their work within the broader context of the field and highlight the significance of their research questions. Rural libraries are essential community resources that provide access to information and resources for residents in remote areas. Despite facing challenges such as limited funding and outdated technology, rural libraries have a positive impact by promoting literacy, supporting education, and fostering community. They also face unique challenges in serving diverse populations due to limited transportation and internet access. Some rural libraries have implemented innovative programs like bookmobiles and mobile hotspots to address these challenges. Further research is needed to explore the impact of rural libraries on the well-being of residents and identify best practices for supporting and sustaining their services.

REFERENCES

- [1] Ajuwon, G. A. (2006). Alternative Strategies for HIV/AIDS Information Dissemination in Nigerian Rural Communities. *Journal of Hospital Librarianship* , 6 (2), 27-41.
- [2] Akinbile, L. A. (2008). Assessment of Extension Agents Knowledge in the Use of Communication Channels for Agricultural Information Dissemination in Ogun State, Nigeria. *Journal of Agricultural & Food Information* , 341-353.
- [3] Alemna, A. A. (1991). Library education and rural information provision in Ghana. *Information Development* , 7 (3), 147-150.
- [4] Anwar, M. A., & Supaat, H. I. (1998). Information needs of rural Malaysians: an exploratory study of a cluster of three villages with no library service. *International Information & Library Review* , 23-36.
- [5] Asaba, J. F., & all, e. (2006). Bridging the Information and Knowledge Gap between Urban and Rural Communities through Rural Knowledge Centres: Case Studies from Kenya and Uganda. *Quarterly Bulletin of the International Association of Agricultural Information Specialists* , 143-151.
- [6] Asamoah-Hassan, H. R. (1997). Information for the rural person in Ghana. Strategies for dissemination. *Information Development* , 13 (3), 122-127.
- [7] Balakrishnan, S., & Paliwal, P. (2001). *Library Administration and Resources*. New Delhi: Anmol Publications Pvt. Ltd.
- [8] Benstead, K., Spacey, R., & Goulding, A. (2004). Changing public library service delivery to rural communities in England. *New Library World* , 400-409.
- [9] Clarke, C., Yu, L., Yu, C., & Fu, L. (2011). How Far Can We Go in Ensuring Equality of Access to Public Library Services? The Re-Visitation of a Core Professional Value in the Context of Regional and Urban-Rural Inequalities in China. *Libri: International Journal of Libraries & Information Services* , 23-36.
- [10] De Jager, K., & Nasslmbenl, M. (2007). Information Literacy in Practice: engaging public library workers in rural South Africa. *IFLA Journal* , 313-322.
- [11] Dent, V. F. (2007). Local economic development in Uganda and the connection to rural community libraries and literacy. *New Library World* , 203-217.
- [12] Devi, T. R. (2007). Towards promotion and dissemination of indigenous knowledge: A case of NIRD. *International Information & Library Review* , 185-193.

Rural Libraries in Chikkaballapur District: Broadcasting Economic Information to Rustical
Communities – A Literature Survey

- [13] Durrani, S. (1985). Rural information in Kenya, rural information and advice services, information services in the Eastern Pilbara. *Information Development* , 149-168.
- [14] Ebiwolate, P. B. (2010). Nigeria Public Library Service to Rural Areas: Libraries in Niger Delta States. *Library Philosophy & Practice* , 12 (2), 5.
- [15] Etebu, A. T. (2009). Information for Rural Communities: A Solution for Sustainable Development in the Niger Delta. *Library Philosophy & Practice* , 11 (2), 1-5.
- [16] Gadagin, B. R., & Kamble, V. T. (2008). Role of Community Information Centres in Rural Development: A State-of- the-Art in Karnataka. *SRELS Journal of Information Management* , 419-428.
- [17] Gardner, M. (2000). Information and Resources for Rural Areas. *Journal of Agricultural & Food Information* , 11.
- [18] Houlahan, J. M. (1980). Current trends in rural public library services. *Library Trends* , 360-366.
- [19] Islam, M. S., & Ahmed, S. Z. (2012). Rural library services II An empirical assessment of information provision in rural communities in northern districts of Bangladesh. *New Library World* , 364-384.
- [20] Islam, M. S., & Uddin, M. H. (2005). Information Support Services of the Rural Development Libraries in Bangladesh. *Malaysian Journal of Library & Information Science* , 105-116.
- [21] Jatana, M., & Khosla, S. (2003). Public Library-A Dynamic Community Centre for Socio-Cultural Uplift of Rural India. *Herald of Library Science* , 66-74.
- [22] Juma, D., & Kahinga, E. (2006). Rural Development Networks Online: A Web-based Agricultural Information System. *Quarterly Bulletin of the International Association of Agricultural Information Specialists* , 248-255.
- [23] Kaula, P. N. (2006). Need And Development of Libraries In Rural India. *Herald of Library Science* , 52-59.
- [24] Kiplang'at, J. (1999). An analysis of the opportunities for information technology in improving access, transfer and the use of agricultural information in the rural areas of Kenya. *Library Management* , 115-127.
- [25] Kiplang'at, J. (1999). An analysis of the opportunities for information technology in improving access, transfer and the use of agricultural information in the rural areas of Kenya. *Library Management* , 20 (2), 115-127.
- [26] Kumar, S. (2005). . Rural Library and Community Resource Centres (Rlcrs) in India with Special Reference to States Having Library Legislation: Problems and Prospects. *SRELS Journal of Information Management* , 275-280.
- [27] Kunhambu, K., & Mudhol, M. V. (2012). Role of Rural Libraries in Rural Areas. *SRELS Journal of Information Management* , 631-647.
- [28] Kurnar, S. (2006). A Journey of Rural Library Movement in India: Retrospect and Prospects. *SRELS Journal of Information Management* , 295-306.
- [29] Mária, R. (2007). A new model of providing library services in rural areas — the Library Service System for Rural Areas in Bács-Kiskun County. *Tudományos es Muszaki Tajekoztatas* , 195-204.
- [30] Mehra, B., Black, K., Singh, V., & Nolt, J. (2011). Collaborations Between LIS Education and Rural Libraries in the Southern and Central Appalachia: Improving Librarian Technology Literacy and Management Training. *Journal of Education for Library & Information Science* , 238-247.
- [31] Mokgaboki, S. (2002). Extending community library and information services to rural areas the challenges that lie ahead. *South African Journal of Libraries & Information Science* , 8.

- [32] Ray, P. P., Biswas, B. C., & Sen, B. K. (2005). Knowledge Communication in Tagore's Model for Rural Reconstruction: An Overview. *Annals of Library & Information Studies* , 52 (3), 94-102.
- [33] Shaifuddin, N., Ahmad, M., & Mokhtar, W. H. (2011). Rural Youth's Perceptions of Information Sources and Rural Library Services. *Library Philosophy & Practice* , 176-194.
- [34] Shivalingappa, A., & Tadasad, P. G. (2009). Status of Rural Librarianship - Gram Panchayat Library System in Hyderabad Karnataka Region. *SRELS Journal of Information Management* , 189-194.
- [35] Snyder, T. A. (2004). Rural Library Services to Minority Populations: Case Studies in the United States. *Rural Libraries* , 51-63.
- [36] Snyman, M., & Snyman, R. (2003). Getting information to disadvantaged rural communities: the centre approach. *South African Journal of Libraries & Information Science* , 95-107.
- [37] Spatz, M. A. (2000). Providing consumer health information in the rural setting: Planetree Health Resource Center's approach. *Bulletin of the Medical Library Association* , 88 (4), 382-388.
- [38] Standerfer, A. E. (2006). Reference Services in Rural Libraries. *Reference Librarian* , 137-149.
- [39] Sturges, P., & Chimseu, G. (1996). The chain of information provision in the villages of Malawi: a rapid rural appraisal. *International Information & Library Review* , 28 (2), 135-156.
- [40] Takalkar, S. A., & Devi, T. R. (2001). Rural Libraries- A Comparative Study in Four States of India. *Public Library Quarterly* , 43-55.
- [41] Uhegbu, A. (2001). Deterrents to information service for community development. *Library Review* , 237-242.
- [42] Unagha, A. O., & Ibenne, S. K. (2011). Obstacles to Provision and Use of Development Information in Rural Communities in Nigeria. *Library Philosophy & Practice* , 320-325.
- [43] Vavrek, B. (1995). Rural information needs and the role of the public library. *Library Trends* , 21-28.
- [44] Zabed Ahmed, S. M. (2010). Measuring performance and impact of rural community-led library initiatives in Thailand. *Information Development*, 17-35.

Citation: Ravikumar, N.S., & Ningayya. (2024). Rural libraries in Chikkaballapur district: Broadcasting economic information to rustical communities – A literature survey. *Journal of Library and Information Science Technology*, 6(2), 14–27.

Article Link:

https://iaeme.com/MasterAdmin/Journal_uploads/JLIST/VOLUME_6_ISSUE_2/JLIST_06_02_002.pdf

Abstract Link:

https://iaeme.com/Home/article_id/JLIST_06_02_002

Copyright: © 2024 Authors. This is an open-access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author and source are credited.

This work is licensed under a **Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License (CC BY 4.0)**.

✉ editor@iaeme.com